

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF LABOR

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ABSTRACT

Motherhood is important part of women's life, without which her existence is felt as a meaningless, though becoming a mother is a beautiful dream of every woman but there is always a fearful about the mode and complication of labor. Acharya Kashyapa explained as "During labour her one leg is in this loka and another leg is in Yama loka." Most of the maternal deaths are due to preventable causes such as PPH, infection, obstructed labour. In India in every 10 minutes a women dies due to pregnancy and child birth complication. For completion of labour normalcy of Vata is essential which can be achieved through proper Garbhini Paricharya. Different stages of Prasava and its Paricharya is explained by our Acharyas. Vitiation of Vata causes Prasava Sanga and its management is also explained in classics. Treatment of placental retention and its treatment are explained like Yoni Dhupan and etc. So, in this direction this paper is highlighting the concept of Garbha and Prasava in detail as well as its management told in our classics.

KEYWORDS: Prasava, PPH, Apanvata, Sanga, Garbha.

INTRODUCTION

Labour pain is always been concern to mankind. It is an anticipatory self-limiting normal process which ends with the birth of a baby and expulsion of the placenta, requiring minimal assistance and supervision. Labor pain that results from both psychic and reflex action can be divided in to three categories emotional, functional, and psychological.^[1]

Child birth and delivery are unique events in women's life. If not dealt with well, it could lead to unpleasant experiences and mental agony, despite several advances in medicine the ideal management of mother with labor pain remains one of the most important issues of health care system in many countries.^[2]

Ayurveda has given much importance to Prasava, and describes the stages of Prasava like Prajayani, Upasthita Prasava. For Prasava, proper functioning of Apanvata is highly essential.^[3]

Nirukti of Prasava

मर्म मोचनम तत् पर्यभर् प्रसूतत (शब्ध कल्प द्रुम)^[4]

Mochana means Moksha i.e. Moksha from Garbhavasa. Importance of Prasava was given since Vedic period. In Rigveda, Aswini kumars did Suka Prasava of Vaghrimati and in Atharvaveda, Garbha was said to be Nivas for

Devas and we have the reference of prasava in Samhita kala explained prasava kala, prasava lakshanas, Prasava paricahrya, sutika paricahrya.^[5]

Labour is very much unpredictable to foretell the exact onset, our Acharyas explained duration of normal labour as navam & dhasham masa, if delivery is not happen in these period then Garbha said to be vikruta.^[3]

Prasava hetu

According to Acharya Sushruta, the fruit detaches from its stalk due to time factor comes down naturally, similarly the Garbha detaches from its nadi nibhadhan, due to its specific nature.^[6] Harita quoted Garbha- Vasa Vairagya as one of the cause for prasava.^[7]

Bhela explained after attending Sampurnata by fetus then only prasava proceeds.^[8]

Clinical features of Prajayini - Women having laxity of kuksi, release of bond of hridaya and pain in thighs and Bhavaprakasha termed this stage as prasvotsuka.^[9]

Clinical features of Asanna/ Upasthita prasava - Recurrent severe pain around back and sacrum, excretion of faeces and urine with increased frequency and mucoid discharges per vagina.^[10]

Importance of Garbhini Paricharya in Prasava

According to Acharya Charak there is no cause greater than Vata in manifestation of disease and there is no better remedy than Basti.

8th month Garbhini Parichary

If Vata is functioning normal than lady delivers without difficulty & remains free from complication. Asthapana basti (badhari, bala, atibala, shatpuspha, mastu, milk, curd) followed by Anuvasan basti (with milk & decoction of drugs of madhura dravyas). For internally sinigdha yavagu, & mamsa rasa of wild animals, due to this her body becomes snigdha & gains strength, and delivers normally without complication.^[11]

9 month paricharya- Anuvasan basti prepared from madhura dravyas, for internally Meat soup with cooked rice and fat or rice gruel mixed with good quantity of fat should be given. Yoni pichu should be used for lubrication of Garbhasthana & Garbharmarga.^[12]

Management of Labour

After onset of labor pains, the women should be made to sit on a soft cushion spreaded over ground. Woman having the experience of conducting labour should encircle and encourage the women by consoling with pleasant words. After descending of the head, the women should be made to lie down on the bed & be advised to bear down. Attender should recite repeatedly the mantra Panchamahabhut & prajapathi should protect you & make you free from this shalya.^[13]

Women should be encircled by kumaras & hold the fruit bearing masculine name. Abhyanga followed by bath with lukewarm water & made to drink yavagu, and sleep in supine position with flexed thighs on a soft bed having pillow & be attended by mature, expert four women having their nails trimmed, after descending, pleasing massage should do on genitalias.^[14]

He specified the Kautuka mangala, soft cushion spreaded over the ground covered with skin of red bull and women attending her should wear intact cloths. Women should be given with inhalation of powered like Kusta, Ela, Langali, Vacha, Chatraka, cirabilva. Or intermittent inhalation of smoke of Bhurjapatra or leaves of Simsipa, Sarjarasa.^[15]

Attender should console, encourage and delight pregnant woman, narrate to her pleasures of children and sorrows of childless couple. Use of meat soup during Prasava kala, Woman anxious to delivery should be remain happy free from shyness & encircled with old women.^[16]

CAUSE & MANAGEMENT OF DELAYED LABOR

शुक्रस् शीघ्रमुत्सर्गं सङ्गं विकृततमे िय ॥

1) Drugs used for Yoni Dhoopan/Lepana^[17]

Fumigation with slough of black snake or Pinditaka should be done.

Paste of root Potaki kalka + Tila Tail application inside

the vaginal canal brings easy delivery

2) Amulet of drugs or Anointment over parts of body^[18]

Root of Hiranyapushpi should be tied over arms or legs or Suvarcala or Visalya should be used. Root of Iksu measuring to the length of women should be tied in waist, Root of Langali, Pratyakpushpa, Paribhadra, or Kakajangha should be tied in waist. Paste of Krisna and Vaca mixed with water and castor oil apply over umbilicus.

Chanting of Mantra helps in delayed labor^[19]: “All the ties and special bonds are realised, the rays have been emitted by sun, the fetus is now free from all fears, now do not delay do not delay”

3) Oral medication^[20]- Root powered of Matulunga + Madhuyasti + Ghrita helps for sukaprasava.

Placental Expulsion

Charaka says that after delivery of fetus one of the attendants inspect carefully that whether placenta is expelled or not

Treatment for Retained Placenta^[21]

Vitiation of Vayu is main etiological factor for retention of placenta, with its suppression placenta comes out immediately

External manipulations for placental expulsion^[22]

Compressing forcefully the abdomen of delivered women over umbilicus and holding her by back or holding her by both the arms violent jerks should be given. The attendant should compress repeatedly the pelvis of the delivered woman. Throat and palate should be touched with braid of hair or a finger wrapped with hair. Throat should be touched with braid of hair.

2) Vaginal fumigation to expel the placenta^[23]

a) Bhurjapatra, kakamachi and slough of snake
b) Bhurjapatra and Guggulu, vaginal massage with Shalmali ghrita and fumigation with Nimba, Katukalabu, slough of snake.

3) Vaginal application^[24]- Kalka of Guda + Shunti lepa, Bhurja patra, Langali, Tumbi, Sarpa twak, Kusta, Sarshapa

4) Applications and irrigation of drugs^[25]- Root paste of Langali applied on hands and over stomach. Irrigation with latex of Mahavrksa overhead.

5) Vaginal tampon^[26]- Tampon soak with oil prepared with Satapushpa, Kusta, Madanphala and Hingu. Above drugs used for Anuvasan basti. Siddartaka, Kusta, Langali, latex of Mahavrksa mixed with Surmanda used for Anuvasan basti.

6) Manual removal of placenta^[27]- Lubricated hand

and trimmed nail should be inserted following umbilical cord and remove placenta and membrane.

CONCLUSION

1. Labour events have got great psychological, emotional & social impact to the woman & her family she experience stress, the care giver should be tactful, sensitive & respectful to her.
2. Proper understanding of the mechanism of labour helps to guide obstetrician to differentiate normal from abnormal condition during process of labour to avoid the complication either mother or fetus.
3. For Prasava, proper functioning of Apanvata is highly essential, for maintaining normalcy of Vata proper Garbhini Paricharya should be followed as told in our classics.
4. Procedures conducting were, maintaining the normalcy of Vata and most of the drugs used in management of labour were Garbhashayo- Uttejaka due to its Tikshana Guna and Prabhava.
5. Further research should be conduct to know the mode of action & pharmacological action of the drugs.
6. By studying only one science a man can never catch the true import of science, so one should study the allied branches as much as possible.

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